

How does the mandatory International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption influence accounting-based measures of performance in firms of PSX: The Complementary function of the CG Index?

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this paper is to study the effect of IFRS adoption on the accounting base performance in Pakistani non-financial registered firms in the presence of moderating influence of the CG index. We use internal financial reporting standards (IFRS) as an independent variable, accounting base performances (ROA & ROE) as a dependent variable, Corporate governance index (CGI) as a moderator, and an index through PCA constructed for the corporate governance mechanism. IFRS is a dummy variable, and the firm size, growth in sales, and financial leverage as control variables. The sample of this study is obtained from the PSX-100 index, containing the top & highest-ranked fifty non-financial firms from 2013 to 2022.

The study employs various estimators including Pooled OLS, Random Effects, and Fixed Effects to ascertain which model well predicts outcomes. The Fixed Effects Model estimates better coefficients than the others in light of respective tests. The results demonstrate that IFRS and accounting-based performance are positively associated. It has also come to know that CGI has positively moderated the association of IFRS and Accounting base performance. Policymakers are required to focus accounting policies and standards mainly on the firms in highly competitive industries to get maximum progress therefrom. Moreover, they also need to formulate the best financial strategies and improve anti-trust laws to upturn the level of competition in all industries in the context of Pakistan. This study has an immense influence on encouraging non-adopter countries to adopt IFRS for the transparency of financial information.

Keywords: IFRS adoption, accounting-base performance, CG Index, Agency issue, Principle Component Analysis (PCA), PSX

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1. Introduction

Financial statements of all financial companies are the crucial part of accounting information.

Financial statements are prepared by businesses to share earnings inflows. Earning inflows convey the financial performance (ROA & ROE) of the companies. Earnings information (inflow) is one of the key alarms in financial disclosure (Yousaf Khan, Ahmad, & Malik, 2021). The earning information in different shapes especially in financial statements should be disclosed according to the principles of accounting. Such statements are prepared by the all financial companies for the provision to concerned stakeholders of the companies which may help to address the level of asymmetry between two well-known parties (Principal and Agent of companies). Because the higher quality of financial statement (accounting information) results in lower asymmetrical information between the shareholders and their agents of companies on one hand and announce best consequences of accounting-based measures of performance (Return on equity and assets) (Ebaid, 2022a; Sukmawati & Pujiningsih, 2022).

IFRS is announced IASB by renewing the International Accounting Standards (IAS) in 2005 to empower the users of financial information. Pakistan as a developing country has made many changes after the issuance of IFRS by IASB. SECP has engaged the firms to adopt the IFRS under section 234 of companies' ordinance 1984. IFRS is a complete set International Accounting Standards. The introduction of IFRS has an important implication on the way financial statements are interpreted, and enhancing understanding by which stakeholders, investors, creditors, banks, governmental agencies to employees, and others make the necessary financial comparability (Nwaogwugwu, 2020; O Cualain & Tawiah, 2023). Therefore, tremendous scholarly attention in all countries has been paid to accounting standards (IFRS/IAS) as a way to boost accounting-based performance. Considerable research (Khan, Ahmad, & Malik, 2022; Schmidhuber, Hilgers, & Hofmann, 2022) have shown that the use of accounting standards and techniques has an impact on the financial performance of widely owned public companies (Cheng, 2019; Khan, Ahmad, & Malik, 2022; Ma et al., 2022). Today due to the globalization in view of global economy the environment of businesses have been changed thoroughly. All internationally businesses are being carried out throughout the nations with one click without travelling distance across. So businesses in presence of globalization have been forced to avoid national system of accounting (national developed standards) for preparation of financial statement. Because the standards of accounting of one country is different from another countries due to multi factors including culture, economy, legal and the like which may adversely affect the understanding of stakeholders of the different countries (Imhanzenobe, 2022) because it did not ensure information uniformity. Consequently, IFRS has been developed and is now regarded as a worldwide business language that enables all stakeholders to comprehend and contrast global commercial situations. IFRS today acts as a standard for evaluating the performance of businesses regardless of the country to which they belong and enables shareholders to understand the genuine financial situation of companies doing business internationally (Ebaid, 2022a; Ma et al., 2022). IFRS are guidelines established by the International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) to help firms prepare financial statements that would accurately reflect all relevant financial and non-financial information for the use of investors and other stakeholders to arrive at economic decisions (GS et al., 2022). Therefore, IFRSs are largely regarded as a set of international standards and are currently utilized in over 120 different countries for general reporting purposes. (Byers, 2017).

Corporate governance practices that are efficient and effective serve to balance the interests of managers and stockholders (Desrousseaux, 2017). Directors of the company are responsible for defining the company's objectives and strategies and advocating their

application (Khan, Ahmad, & Malik, 2022). CGI index also used which is adopted from the research study of Yousaf Khan et al. (2021). CG index has been constructed by using the nine (9) elements of corporate governance (CG) as following equation:

$$\text{CGI} = \Sigma [w_1\text{BoardInd} + w_2\text{BoarSize} + w_3\text{BoardRem} + w_4\text{BoardGenderDiv} + w_5\text{BoardActi} + w_6\text{InsidShareOwnership} + w_7 \text{InstShareOwnership} + w_8 \text{ForeignShareOwnership} + w_9\text{ShareOwnershipConcentration}]$$

The weighted average (WAVG) of all the CG dimensions mentioned above has been used for producing the CG index. PCA is used to assign weight to each item. The degree of corporate governance increases as the calculated score of elements raises. The higher index score for each CG mechanism denotes better construction, which could improve corporate governance effectiveness in entities.

Two financial performance metrics, ROA and ROE, are tested and examined in this research study. ROA in fact reflects the efficient way management uses the company's resources to produce a return in the form of earnings or profit. Return on equity (ROE) is a financial and accounting metric that indicates the profitability of the investments made by investors. Accounting-based performance measurements result from ROA and ROE that are adequately applied to IFRS and corporate governance in the particular firms.

Several researchers (Ebaid, 2022a; O Cualain & Tawiah, 2023) have conducted their research in accounting to address the consequences of IFRS adoption over different metrics of economy. For example, it was found in different results of researchers that IFRS adoption has positive impact on accounting quality (Ahmed, Neel, & Wang, 2013; Key & Kim, 2020; Pășcan, 2015), improve market and stock liquidity (Firoz, 2022; Silva & Nardi, 2020), improved analysts forecasts (Miah, Jiang, Rahman, & Stent, 2023), report positive impact on financial reporting quality (Apochi & Mustapha, 2022; Egiyi, 2022), reduce the cost of equity of shareholders (Worku, 2022; Zaro, Flores, Fasan, Murcia, & Zaro, 2022), enhance transparency of financial reports (Riaz, Ray, & Ray, 2022), increase Audit Report Lag (ARL) (Gamra, Hamza, & Borgi, 2022), increase foreign mutual fund ownership (DeFond, Hu, Hung, & Li, 2011; Ebaid, 2022a) and IFRS also boost the value of equity, assets and firms' net income (M. Hung & Subramanyam, 2007). Unlike some research studies argue that implementation of IFRS results in decrease in shareholders' equity and firms' profit, and lead to enhance in firms' liabilities and leverage ratios (M. Hung & Subramanyam, 2007; Morales-Díaz & Zamora-Ramírez, 2018). Dalcı and Özyapıcı (2017) documented in this regard that IFRS has no influence on solvency, liquidity and profitability ratios. Ebaid (2022a) documented that there is no significant differences between the values of accounting-based performance measures (profitability, liquidity and leverage) and IFRS in Saudi Arabia firms. In light of these mixed results, this study aims to examine the impact of the adoption of IFRS on the accounting based performance of listed companies in the PSX in presence of corporate governance index (CGI).

This research study differs from past research in several respects including 1- This study examines the direct impact of IFRS on accounting-based performance measurements. 2- This study also employs a moderating variable (CGI) to examine the indirect influence of IFRS on accounting performance. 3- This study has adopted corporate governance index 4- This study made use of the most recent Panel data of non-financial registered companies.

We conducted the study with the understanding that such studies are uncommon in economically deprived countries such as Pakistan. As therefore, it is a new emerging subject matter. In view of these mixed outcomes, the purpose of this study is to examine the impact of IFRS adoption on accounting-based metrics of performance of PSX-listed companies. In addition, this study examines the moderating effect of the CG index on the relationship between IFRS adoption and accounting-based indicators of performance. As a result, this study fills the previously identified study gap and is useful for shareholders,

stakeholders, management, and policymakers in South Asia's non-financial industries, particularly in Pakistan. The majority of studies in the developed world regard IFRS as a significant indication or factor of financial success that provides a corporation with a competitive advantage. The majority of studies on the subject have focused on the rich world and made recommendations for emerging countries. Pakistan is a developing country in which corporations are tirelessly trying to implement accounting standards and procedures in order to promote transparency and the disclosure of information for the betterment of their corporate sectors and to figure out the desired goals in terms of efficiency at both the market and firm level. In the context of underdeveloped countries as opposed to the industrialized world, some studies confirmed differing outcomes. We test the data to determine which model is most appropriately supported rather than using the blind-eye method for data analysis. We use fixed effects, random effects, and pooled OLS models to forecast outcomes in this regard. The integration of IFRS and accounting-based performance metrics with the Moderator role of the CG Index has not been studied in developing markets, most notably in the context of Pakistan. In addition, we look at the top 50 non-financial enterprises as exemplars of all industries, none of which have been thoroughly studied in the context of Pakistan historically. The goal of the study is to assess the non-financial sector firms' IFRS practices in order to determine their strengths and weaknesses. It also aims to examine the relationship between IFRS and accounting-based performance measures in the presence of a moderating variable called the CG Index in these listed selected firms.

The agency theory, which describes the interaction between the principal and management of a firm, serves as the underpinning framework for this study. Due to their separation and the fact that each party considers their own interests first, agency conflict (information asymmetry) arises between the two sides of the structure. A company of any size can reduce or resolve this issue through its corporate governance (Khan, 2022; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997).

The remaining sections of this research article are organized as follows: The second section describes the literature review; the third section elaborates on the study's methodology; the fourth section focuses on empirical findings and comments, while the fifth section concludes this study.

2. Literature

THEORETICAL LITERATURE

Theory of Agency (ToA):

Alchian and Demsetz first proposed this theory in 1972, and J. and Meckling (1976) subsequently supported it and the issues of the agency came into existence when humans thought about business to maximization of profits with self-interest. (Yousaf Khan et al., 2021). Generally, it explores the relationship between shareholders and top management. The former delegates power to the latter for decision-making to serve on their behalf. However, the latter fails to serve the principal's interest except for his own which may result in agency conflict and asymmetrical information. Investors demand that management should continue the business in that way by which profit maximization can be achieved and returns should be increased as compared to the risk associated with an investment portfolio, but managers of firms want to run the business in that way by which their own interest/power/value/wealth increase as compared to their responsibilities (Khan, Ahmad, & Malik, 2022).

Theory of Stakeholders (ToS)

Stakeholder theory was developed to fill the gap left by Agency theory, which only concentrated on shareholders as the parties that were concerned. In Stakeholder theory, however, several stakeholders are taken into account as the parties who are affected by agency challenges (Saeed, 2020). The theory of stakeholders (TOS) discusses the effects of different actions of a firm on its shareholders. Freeman (2010) has strong confidence that if a business entity wants to become strong by its performance. The firm needs to consider the interests of its participants but if such a firm cannot protect the interests of its stakeholders, then its performance's boat may be drawn into the river of the competition.

Positive accounting theory (PAT)

The approach that should be used is not specified; instead, it represents the forecast of accounting procedures used in firms for their accounting records. The best accounting idea that may be used to accomplish benefits while managers are participating in contracts, according to this theory, is accounting standards. The opportunistic behavior of management is thus preserved by the proposed theory to boost the profitability of pertinent firms (Khan, Ahmad, & Awan, 2022; Khan, Ahmad, Awan, & e Ali, 2022). Furthermore, PAT explains such research literature in which positive accounting theory is being applied to focus on such accounting methods and choices which will be adopted by firms in the future. But it is sorted out in literature that management of firms doesn't take such steps which are in favor of investors. Thus it may result in conflict between the respective parties of firms. The issues in which information asymmetry is always involved between agent and principal by which managers try to enjoy such advantages from the asymmetry of information which may be in favor of their interest as compared to the demand and interest of investors (Watts & Zimmerman, 1986).

Stewardship Theory

According to this theory, the principal-agent relationship is in sync as both parties pursue the interests of the business rather than their own (Subramanian, 2018). Based on the steward's theory, a manager merely represents a person who desires to carry out his duties in a manner that is courteous. The manager should be a steward by his feelings to protect the interests of the firm's shareholders. Furthermore, according to Davis, Schoorman, and Donaldson (1997) the manager as a steward is motivated intrinsically to achieve organizational goals hence, he is bound to add values to the firm where he is serving.

Resource Dependency Theory

The resource dependency theory (RDT) approaches the role of a firm's CGM to arrange the useful resources for the firm. Pfeffer and Gerald (1978) discuss that a firm needs valuable resources that can be gathered from the business environment in which a firm has to work. They must deal with issues of resources because if the managers have a strong interaction with resource providers, then the firm's managers can gather useful resources from them in time to play an effective role in the firm's performance.

EMPERICAL LITERATURE

Accounting standards are employed in firms for preparation of relevant financial statements which depict the financial status and performance of the respective firms. It conveys a green signal that there is nexus between the accounting standards (IFRS) and accounting based performance of firms. The reason behind this nexus that IFRS is an international standards which is totally different from local standards of accounting employed locally. Thus it is expected that adoption of IFRS have critical influence on financial position and accounting based measures of performance.

Therefore, this study is carried out in order to test the direct effect of IFRS on accounting based performance and moderating effect of CGI on their nexus in firms of PSX.

M. Hung and Subramanyam (2007) carried out research study by using sample firms of German for the period from 1998-2002. They found that IFRS adoption has significant effect on TA, BV and Income of sample firms.

Dalcı and Özyapıcı (2017) conducted their research study in sample firms Turkey. They examined to check the influence on IFRS adoption on different dependent variables including profitability, liquid and solvency. They documented that IFRS adoption could not influence financial ratios of listed firms of Turkey for the period under study.

Nwaogwugwu (2020) conducted research study in Nigeria by examining the impact of IFRS on ROA, ROE and earning per share. They used panel data for the purpose of analysis. They have used the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) as the appropriate estimator for analysis of the data. They concluded that the adoption of IFRSs could not result in higher performance and increased value. The same findings also documented by Akinleye (2016).

Jindrichovska and Kubícková (2014) and studied the influence of IFRS on financial performance in United Kingdom (UK). They found mixed findings from their research study i.e., as all profitability ratios pictured significant upturn, liquidity ratios specified insignificant rise, whereas the market-based ratio disclosed insignificant decrease.

Fitó, Moya, and Orgaz (2013) and Khan, Zafar, and Ayaz (2022) conducted their study in Spain in order to check the influence of IFRS on accounting ratios and accounting numbers. They found a significant influence in pertinent variable of the study (Hasan & Rahman, 2020).

Das and Srivastava (2023) investigate the impact of IFRS on the financial (accounting) performance and reporting of Indian firms. Their sample period is from 2015 to 2021 for analysis of sample firms. Their findings indicate that IFRS has significantly influence on financial reporting and financial information.

Jin (2017) used Canadian firms and Munteanu, Brad, Ciobanu, and Dobre (2014) used Romanian firms in order to know the influence of IFRS adoption on ROE. They figured out in this regard that IFRS is positively (+ve) marks the rate of ROE. In simple terms, the adoption of IFRS causes the corresponding Canadian and Romanian firms to achieve greater rates of return on equity.

Ndori Queku et al. (2023) carried out research study to investigate the influence IFRS adoption on the level of tax revenue performance in Africa. They documented data from six African countries for the analyses from 1996 to 2020. The paper employs PMG and DOLS as estimators. The results demonstrated that IFRS implementation could pose a serious risk to the effective use of tax revenue in Africa, as shown by the highly negative long-term forecasts. The findings also showed that IFRS had significant short-term effects.

Given the divergent findings of previous studies on the consequence of IFRS on corporate accounting oriented performance. Therefore, this study aims to examine the direct impact of the mandatory adoption of IFRS on accounting-based performance measures and also the moderating influence of CGI on their nexus for listed companies of Pakistani industries. Thus this study aims to test statistically the following four hypotheses:

Hypothesis:

- (i) There is positive relationship between IFRS adoption and ROA in sampled firms of PSX
- (ii) There is positive relationship between IFRS adoption and ROE in sampled firms of PSX
- (iii) CG Index positively moderates the association between IFRS adoption & ROA in sampled firms.
- (iv) CG Index positively moderates the relationship between IFRS adoption & ROE in sampled firms.

Research Framework

3. Research Methodology

Sample Size and Data Collection

The top listed companies on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX) between 2010 and 2023 make up the study's sample. Financial, insurance, and other such companies are specifically excluded. Only 50 of the top non-financial enterprises are taken into account in this study. Due to major structural and reporting differences, data should only be gathered from non-financial sectors. Data for the relevant variable was taken from reports of non-financial firms that were posted to the Pakistan Exchange website. Precisely, the study includes 50 top non-financial firms listed in Pakistan stock exchange (PSX) for 12 years i.e. (50*12) = 600 firms years observation.

Variables, their operational definition and measurements

There are dependent, independent, moderating and control variables used in this research paper of the study. IFRS is used as independent variable, accounting based financial performance is used as dependent variable. It is further categorized into two sub-variables which are ROA and ROE of respective firms. The CGI is used as moderating variable of the study. Control variables are firm size, sale growth and leverage of respective firms.

IFRS adopted as independent variable in this study which is being estimated by considering as a dummy Variable. If a company reported its financial statements adopting IFRS, it was recorded as one; otherwise, it was marked as zero

ROA is measured by dividing the net profit on the firm's assets (Net profit /Total assets) while ROE is calculated by dividing the profit by the equity of shareholders of the firm (profit/ equity).

Following Saeed (2020) and Khan, Ahmad, and Malik (2022), this study has also constructed CG Index. CG index has been developed from nine indicators of corporate governance. CG index has been constructed by using the nine characteristics of firm governance.

$$CGI = \sum [w_1BoardInd + w_2BoarSize + w_3BoardRem + w_4BoardGenderDiv + w_5BoardActi + w_6InsidShareOwnership + w_7InstShareOwnership + w_8ForeignShareOwnership + w_9ShareOwnershipConcentration]$$

The WAVG of each of the CG dimensions listed above was used to develop the CG index. PCA has been used to assign weights to the parameters. The degree of CG varies with the size of the calculated component score. Every CG mechanism's higher index score denotes improved construction that could contribute to impactful CG.

Following previous studies ((Ayaz, Khan, & Shad, 2022; Khan, Ahmad, & Malik, 2022; Saeed, 2020), three control variables such as Firm size; Leverage and Growth are used in this paper. The first variable is computed as the log of the total assets of each firm. The second is determined by calculating the total sales of the respective firms by their percentage increase. To calculate the third variable, divide the firm's total liabilities by its total assets.

Model Specification

This study uses three models to test the hypotheses and pooled OLS, random effects, and fixed effects models are used to estimate the parameters of the models. The findings of the Hausman test are used to decide the efficiency of the methods mentioned above.

Model (1)

This first model is formed to examine how IFRS will impact on ROA. To ascertain their impact on asset return on investment, control factors are also included.

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IFRS_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + \beta_4 Gn_{it} + e_{it}$$

Model (2)

The following second model is formed to ascertain the impact of IFRS on ROE in presence of control variables.

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IFRS_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + \beta_4 Gn_{it} + e_{it}$$

Model (3)

This third model is established to examine the moderating impact of CGI on the relationship between IFRS and ROA. In order to ascertain their impact on return on assets, control variables are also incorporated.

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IFRS_{it} + \beta_2 CGI_{it} + \beta_3 IFRS_{it} * CGI_{it} + \beta_4 SIZE_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \beta_6 Gn_{it} + e_{it}$$

Model (4)

The following fourth model is formed to test the moderating effect of CGI on the nexus between IFRS and ROE. Control variables are included to determine their influence on return on equity.

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IFRS_{it} + \beta_2 CGI_{it} + \beta_3 IFRS_{it} * CGI_{it} + \beta_4 SIZE_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \beta_6 GnS_{it} + e_{it}$$

4. Analysis along with discussion**Diagnostic tests**

The sample data used for this research study has to undergo a number of diagnostic tests in order for the analysis to be viable. In truce with past studies, the sample data was put through a diagnostic process provided in Table 1 hereunder. (Alkordi, Munther, & Dabaghia, 2017; Khan, Ahmad, & Malik, 2022).

Table 1: Diagnostic-Tests

Particular	Test	X2	Prob. Chi Sq.	VIF	1/VIF	F	Prob
Normality	Jarque-Bera test	0.503	0.301	-	-	-	-
Serial-Correlation	Breusch-Godfrey LM test	0.073	0.132	-	-	-	-
Heteroscedasticity	Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test	0.703	0.523	-	-	-	-
Multicollinearity	VIF (IFRS)	-	-	1.01	0.988711	-	-
	VIF (CGI)	-	-	1.09	0.918231	-	-
	VIF (CGI*IFRS)	-	-	1.66	0.907646	-	-
	VIF (FirmS)	-	-	1.05	0.956774	-	-
	VIF (Levrg)	-	-	1.04	0.965708	-	-
	VIF (GnS)	-	-	1.02	0.97666	-	-
Endogeneity	RESET test	-	-	-	-	2.25	0.0310

Descriptive Statistics

The total number of observations, mean, and standard deviation values for the study's sample variables are shown in Table 3. The smallest and highest values of the sample data from this study are highlighted in the table of descriptive statistics. The term "arithmetic mean" is also used to refer to the mean or arithmetic average. It is calculated by adding up each number in a set of data, then dividing that total by the number of items in the dataset. The standard deviation specifically depicts how widely dispersed your data is from the mean (Guo, Shi, Rus, & Yau, 2022; Khan, 2019; Khan, Rehman, Shah, & Khan, 2018).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	0.0988	0.1174	-0.1000	1.0600
ROE	0.2660	0.2775	-0.1100	0.5600
IFRS	-0.0344	0.1506	-0.9000	0.8300
CGI	0.1423	0.116	0.1000	0.9700
FirmS	10.4437	0.5920	7.1700	12.0500
Levrg	0.4768	0.2723	0.0500	0.2421
Grwth	0.4542	0.7873	0.0000	0.5600

Correlation

Correlation is a statistical method (technique) that explains the association between two variables and proves whether there is an association at all as well as how strongly,

moderately, or weakly it is associated. It illustrates how strongly the variables are correlated. a statistical measure that shows the interdependence of two or more variables. The presentation of some preliminary evidence supporting the study's hypotheses requires the use of correlation coefficients. From -1 to +1, the correlation's value falls inside this range. A significant but positive correlation between the variables is shown by values closer to +1, whereas a significant but negative correlation is shown by values closer to -1 (Cohen, 1988). A correlation coefficient value between .01 and 0.29 indicates a weak relationship between the variables, a value between 0.3 and 0.69 indicates a moderate relationship, and a value between 0.7 and 1.0 indicates a strong relationship between the variables. The value 0 (zero) indicates that there is no linear correlation between the required variables of the study.

Table 2: Pearson correlation matrix

Variable	ROA	ROE	CONACC	CGI	FirmS	Levrg	Grwth
ROA	1						
ROE	0.311	1					
IFRS	0.483	0.4554	1				
CGI	0.472	0.4622	0.494	1			
FirmS	-0.0820	-0.0541	-0.042	-0.0234	1		
Levrg	0.1849	0.1520	-0.0835	0.149	0.164	1	
Grwth	0.259	-0.0458	-0.0669	.246	0.135	0.0522	1

Sig. Levels: *** p<0.1 (1%), ** p<0.05 (5%), * p<0.01 (10%),

Table 4 depicts a correlation matrix that illustrates the association and pattern throughout all study variables. The correlation matrix displays a value of .483 which demonstrates that IFRS and ROA have a substantial positive association, supporting the hypothesis H1 of the study. Similar to the relation between IFRS and ROE, the association between IFRS and ROE is similarly positive (0.4554), providing strong evidence for our study's second hypothesis (H2) that the implementation of IFRS may increase the scope of ROA and ROE for firms. The association between CGI and ROA and ROE has similar higher results, meaning that improved corporate governance may help to speed up the level of return on assets as well as equity of the respective PSX firms.

Model specification

The repercussions of choosing the right model for the analysis of panel data must be grasped. In order to identify the best model, this study used the Likelihood test between CEM and FEM, the Lagrange multiplier (LM) test between CEM and REM, and the Hausman test between the FEM and REM models. A Likelihood-test was conducted by an expert to determine which of the two-panel data estimate models, CEM or FEM, was the best.

Hypothesis:

Ho: Common Effect Model

H1: Fixed Effect Model

Basis decision:

Ho is accepted if the Chi-square probability is greater than 0.05. Ho value is rejected if the Chi-square probability is less than 0.05. The likelihood test findings matching CEM and FEM are as follows:

Table 3: Results of Likelihood-Test

Effect Test	Statistics	df	Prob
Cross-section F	14.257254	(17.65)	.0000
Chi-square cross-section	142.878554	17	0.000

According to the results of the Chow test in Table 5, the probability is 0.0000 based on the Chi-square value. Based on the results of the Chow test, the Fixed Effect Model is the best panel data estimating model because the likelihood of new Chi-square values being less than 0.05 suggests H_0 is not accepted.

Hausman-Test

The Hausman specification test is then used to determine which of the random effect and fixed effect models is the fit. Given that the p-value is significant, the Hausman test result demonstrates that the fixed effect model is preferable to the Random effect model. Relevant test results in the development of two null and alternate hypotheses, which are as follows (Ko, 2022; Sun, Guo, & Wu, 2022; Yousaf Khan et al., 2021):

H_0 : REM.

H_1 : FEM

Basis decision:

H_0 is acceptable if the possibility chi-square is greater than 0.05. H_0 is disproved if the probability chi-square is less than 0.05.

A fixed effect regression model containing xtreg, a dependent variable, an independent variable, a control variable, and FE has been run in STATA for the purposes of conducting this test. This was then entered into STATA and saved using the command "estimations fixed store." The same random effect model is run in STATA using the xtreg command, followed by the re command, and then saved using the command "estimations random store." Once the fixed and random effect models were operational and stored, the Durbin-Wu-Hauman (DWH) test was performed using the command "Hausman fixed random," and the following result came up:

Table 4: Hausman test

	Coef.
Chi-square test value	32.321
P-value	0.000

The result as it is presented above in table 5 is statistically significant, meaning that the prob value of the Chi Square is less than 5% (.05), which means that the "fixed effect model" is a better model for this study's panel data analysis. We reject H_0 and accept H_1 (alternative) since the p-value is smaller than .05. Relevant tests clearly show that the Hausman test has rejected the random effect model. That is why the use of the fixed effect model has increased (Khan, Ahmad, & Malik, 2022).

Regression Analysis along-with Discussion

Table 5: Result of Fixed Effect Model-I

ROA	Coefficient	Std. Err.	P-value
IFRS	0.296017	0.21770	0.000***
FirmS	0.019515	0.082211	0.812
Levrg	0.041929	0.015546	0.007***
Grwth	-0.016458	0.041570	0.692
Summary	Model-I Diagnostics		
R-value	0.512		
Adj. R-Square	0.321		
F-Statistics	15.481		
Prob > F	0.000		

Table 6 shows the results of hypothesis-1 that explores the effects of IFRS adoption on accounting-based performance as measured by the ROA of the sampled firms of the Pakistan stock exchange for the period concerned. These findings show that the sample businesses' R-value is 51.2%, which is a high value, while the total firms' explanatory power can be determined by an R2 (R-Square) value of 32.1%. These results demonstrate that IFRS describe 32.1% of the change in the ROA in the sample firms of Pakistan. The table further shows that the computed value of F, which is higher, is 15.481. The results show that IFRS significantly improves respective firms' ROA, hence H1 of this study may be confidently accepted. This finding is consistent with those of Akinleye (2016) and Nwaogwugwu (2020) for Nigeria firms. It implies that the statistical model that was tested was appropriate. The table further illustrates that the adoption of IFRS results in a greater rate of return on assets by using regression coefficients to demonstrate that IFRS positively affects the rate of return on assets.

Table 6: Result of Fixed Effect Model-II

ROE	Coefficient	Std. Err.	P-value
IFRS	.2737413	.1996985	0.000***
FirmS	-.1309250	.0754111	0.053*
Levrg	.0539535	.1426038	0.035**
Grwth	-.0768360	.0381314	0.840
Summary	Model-II Diagnostics		
R-value	0.415		
Adj. R-Square	0.291		
F-Statistics	10.501		
Prob > F	0.000		

Table 7 shows the results of our second hypothesis which is 'there is a positive relationship between IFRS adoption and ROE in sampled firms of PSX' where independent variable is IFRS adoption and ROE (which is the second main proxy of accounting based performance) is dependent variable of this article.

The results of this table analysis indicate that the R-value which is 41.5% of the sampled firms of under study emerging country (Pakistan). This value of R-square considered is a higher value. Similarly, explanatory power R2 of the total firms shows 29.1%. These results imply that IFRS explain 29% of the change in the ROE in the respective sample firms. The table also shows that the calculated value of F is 10.501, which is somewhat higher value. The findings specify that IFRS has a significant positive influence on ROE of respective sample firms of Pakistan, thus H2 of this study is also confidently accepted. This findings of this study is line with the results of Jin (2017) for Canadian firms and Munteanu et al. (2014) for Romanian firms. This indicates the suitability of the statistical model used for testing. The table also shows, through regression coefficients, that IFRS positively affects the rate of ROE viz the IFRS adoption results in a higher rate of accounting based performance (ROE) of pertinent Pakistani registered firms.

Table 7: Result of Fixed Effect Model-III

ROA	Coefficient	Std. Err.	P-value
IFRS	.3100243	.2350261	0.001***
CGI	.0464031	.0305242	0.005***
IFRS*CGI	.4668670	.1489788	0.002***
FirmS	.0209960	.0818350	0.007***
Levrg	.0404110	.0154853	0.009***
Grwth	-.012936	.041423	0.755
Summary	Model-III Diagnostics		
R-value	0.615		

Adj. R-Square	0.4013
F-Statistics	32.45
Prob > F	0.000

The above table 8 shows the result of our 3rd hypothesis (H3). The findings of the study indicate that interaction term have a significantly positive influence on ROA. It indicates that Big4 audited entities are more cautious because they focused on opportunistic behavior by managers (Yousaf Khan et al., 2021). The results reveal that the CG Index positively moderates the link between IFRS and ROA in a sample of Pakistan's top non-financial enterprises. It implies that effective company governance has the potential to promote the relationship between IFRS and the degree of ROA (Hasan & Rahman, 2020). It also means that Big4 audit companies reduce information asymmetry between the parties involved (Yousaf Khan et al., 2021). Out-of-control variables like firm size and leverage are positively (+ve) significant, but growth (GnS) is adversely significant with ROA.

Table 8: Result of Fixed effect model-IV

ROE	Coefficient	Std. Err.	P-value
IFRS	.1966638	.3232788	0.000***
CGI	.0190077	.2817276	0.000***
IFRS*CGI	.0685185	1.375023	0.006***
FirmS	-.1307459	.0755308	0.084*
Levrg	.0545332	.1429238	0.053*
Grwth	-.078792	.0382324	0.837
Summary	Model-IV Diagnostics		
R-value	0.705		
Adj. R-Square	0.453		
F-Statistics	36.3		
Prob > F	0.000		

The above table 9 shows the findings of our 4th hypothesis. Findings show that CG Index positively moderates the relationship between IFRS and ROE in sample top firms of Pakistan for the sample period. It points out that the presence of the CG Index can improve the association between IFRS and ROE levels (Hasan & Rahman, 2020). In addition, active corporate governance reduces the amount of information asymmetry between the targeted parties of firms. (Yousaf Khan et al., 2021). Control variables such as Leverage is positively significant whereas firms and growth are negatively associated.

5. Conclusion & Limitations

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) may boost accounting-based performance by addressing information asymmetry and agency problems while restoring shareholder confidence in the individual companies of emerging economies like Pakistan. Financial reporting and corporate disclosures are essential for a company's performance and competitive success in today's cutthroat business environment. The purpose of this study was to look into how international financial reporting standards influence accounting-based performance, such as ROA and ROE. Top non-financial firms were considered as being typical of the other PSX firms. The study's findings are highly consistent with those identified in previous studies (Jin, 2017; Ndori Queku et al., 2023; Nwaogwugwu, 2020) throughout the countries. The findings confirm the findings of earlier research that foresaw similar outcomes, proving that IFRS has a very significant impact on the ROA and ROE of these picked top non-financial companies of PSX (Ebaid, 2022b; Hasan & Rahman, 2020;

D. N. Hung & Van, 2020). As the findings of our study indicated that the IFRS made a substantial effect on ROA and ROE, firms in Pakistan should have well-adequate and internally certified accounting and reporting systems to entice stakeholders' confidence in purchasing shares of the different entities. Such efforts will aid the profit maximization strategies of corporations listed on the PSX, as well as serve as a wake-up call for the rest of the firms in other industries to focus on discloser quality. Based on the findings, the SECP should make several aspects of corporate disclosure mandatory for listed corporations that have registered under it. Furthermore, the current financial reporting of these PSX-registered enterprises has to show compliance with international accounting standards. In addition, non-compliance with accounting rules must result in the de-listing of the firm (s) as a penalty notice if found during an audit by Big4.

One of these limitations is the limited sample size, which is due to the low number of listed firms in Pakistan during the study period. Future research may use larger company sample sizes to achieve more productive outcomes in the studies they conduct. In the historical setting of Pakistan, future studies ought to integrate accounting basis qualities such as persistence, accrual quality, predictability, and smoothness with market base attributes such as accounting conservatism and accounting deadlines. Similar future studies could leverage the moderating and mediating influence of audit quality, investment efficiency, and company disclosure quality. Furthermore, in similar studies, a comparison of the US textile sector with the Pakistan textile sector can be a strong addition to the literature. Furthermore, a comparative analysis of Pakistani textile enterprises and any other advanced country textile firms will yield fresh results. Because our research is limited to top non-financial entities, the findings will not be applicable to other industries. Second, differing variable research procedures and sample sizes could impact the results of the research study.

References

1. Ahmed, A. S., Neel, M., & Wang, D. (2013). Does mandatory adoption of IFRS improve accounting quality? Preliminary evidence. *Contemporary accounting research*, 30(4), 1344-1372.
2. Akinleye, G. T. (2016). Effect of international financial reporting standards (IFRS) adoption on the performance of money deposit banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business, Economics and Accountancy*, 4(4), 87-95.
3. Alkordi, A., Munther, A.-N., & Dabaghia, M. (2017). Accounting conservatism and ownership structure effect: Evidence from industrial and financial Jordanian listed companies. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 7(2), 608-619.
4. Apochi, J. G., & Mustapha, L. O. (2022). IFRS Adoption and Financial Reporting Quality in Nigeria: A Conceptual Approach. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(6), 9-18.
5. Ayaz, B., Khan, Y., & Shad, F. (2022). Investigating the Spillover Effects of the US Interest Rate on CO2 Emissions. A Case of a Developing Country. *Abasyn University Journal of Social Sciences*, 15(2).
6. Byers, R. (2017). Implications of transitioning to IFRS on key financial indicators in the oil and gas production industry. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 17(1), 20-37.
7. Cheng, X. (2019). The Impact of IFRS-based Chinese Accounting Standards on Accounting Conservatism. Anglia Ruskin University.
8. Cohen, J. (1988). Set correlation and contingency tables. *Applied psychological measurement*, 12(4), 425-434.
9. Dalci, İ., & Özyapıcı, H. (2017). Analysis of the impact of first-time mandatory IFRS adoption on financial statements: The case study of the listed hotels in Turkey. *Accounting and Management Information Systems*, 16(1), 5-29.
10. Das, B., & Srivastava, A. (2023). THE IMPACT OF IFRS CONVERGENCE ON THE

- FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF INDIAN IT SECTOR: A CASE STUDY OF WIPRO LTD. EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD), 8(4), 52-58.
11. Davis, J. H., Schoorman, F. D., & Donaldson, L. (1997). Toward a stewardship theory of management. *Academy of Management review*, 22(1), 20-47.
 12. DeFond, M., Hu, X., Hung, M., & Li, S. (2011). The impact of mandatory IFRS adoption on foreign mutual fund ownership: The role of comparability. *Journal of accounting and economics*, 51(3), 240-258.
 13. Desrousseaux, L. (2017). *Three Essays in Governance and Financial Reporting*: HEC Montreal (Canada).
 14. Ebaid, I. E.-S. (2022a). IFRS adoption and accounting-based performance measures: evidence from an emerging capital market. *Journal of Money and Business*.
 15. Ebaid, I. E.-S. (2022b). IFRS adoption and accounting-based performance measures: evidence from an emerging capital market. *Journal of Money and Business*, 2(1), 94-106.
 16. Egiyi, M. A. (2022). The Role of International Reporting Standards (IFRS) in Financial Reporting Quality: Evidence from Nigeria. *Global Journal of Finance and Business Review* | ISSN, 1694, 450X.
 17. Firoz, M. (2022). The impact of IFRS convergence on market liquidity: evidence from India. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*.
 18. Fitó, M. À., Moya, S., & Orgaz, N. (2013). Considering the effects of operating lease capitalization on key financial ratios. *Spanish Journal of Finance and Accounting/Revista Española de Financiación y Contabilidad*, 42(159), 341-369.
 19. Gamra, S. B., Hamza, F., & Borgi, H. (2022). The impact of IFRS adoption and corporate governance mechanisms on audit report lag: evidence from an emerging country. *Journal of Accounting and Management Information Systems*, 21(4), 604-630.
 20. GS, A. D., Istanti, E., Zuhro, D., Susanti, R., Sanusi, R., Sutini, S., & Kusumonegor, B. (2022). COMPARISONAL ANALYSIS OF BANKING FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE BEFORE AND AFTER ADOPTING IFRS. *International Journal of Economics and Management Research*, 1(3), 09-16.
 21. Guo, H., Shi, R., Rus, D., & Yau, W.-Y. (2022). Dual Dynamic Programming for the Mean Standard Deviation Canadian Traveller Problem. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*.
 22. Hasan, M. T., & Rahman, A. A. (2020). The role of corporate governance on the relationship between IFRS adoption and earnings management: Evidence from Bangladesh. *International Journal of Financial Research*, 11(4), 329-345.
 23. Hung, D. N., & Van, V. T. T. (2020). Studying the impacts of earnings quality on stock return: Experiments in Vietnam. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*, 7(4), 45-53.
 24. Hung, M., & Subramanyam, K. (2007). Financial statement effects of adopting international accounting standards: the case of Germany. *Review of accounting studies*, 12, 623-657.
 25. Imhanzenobe, J. (2022). Value relevance and changes in accounting standards: A review of the IFRS adoption literature. *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 2039057.
 26. Jin, Y. (2017). DuPont analysis, earnings persistence, and return on equity: Evidence from mandatory IFRS adoption in Canada. *Accounting Perspectives*, 16(3), 205-235.
 27. Jindrichovska, I., & Kubicková, D. (2014). Impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) adoption on key financial ratios: the case of the Czech Republic. *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, 10(2), 133-146.
 28. Key, K. G., & Kim, J. Y. (2020). IFRS and accounting quality: Additional evidence from Korea. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 39, 100306.
 29. Khan, Y. (2019). CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY, EARNINGS MANAGEMENT AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM PAKISTANI'S REGISTERED FIRMS. *CITY UNIVERSITY JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES*, 1(1).
 30. Khan, Y. (2022). The sophisticated role of accounting information system (AIS) on the performance of Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs): Evidence from an emerging economy. *Competitive Social Science Research Journal*, 3(2), 199-214.
 31. Khan, Y., Ahmad, W., & Awan, S. H. (2022). The Hijab Consumer Attitude toward Hijab

- Fashion Brand: A Case of the Developing Country. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 2(4), 125-137.
32. Khan, Y., Ahmad, W., Awan, S. H., & e Ali, M. S. (2022). Assessing the Relevance of Framing Messages on Backing Intentions in Crowdfunding Social Cause-related Marketing Campaign. *Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 2(3), 55-65.
 33. Khan, Y., Ahmad, W., & Malik, F. (2022). THE INFLUENCE OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE ON ACCOUNTING CONSERVATISM IN TOP NON-FINANCIAL FIRMS OF PSX: THE MODERATING ROLE OF AUDIT QUALITY. *Competitive Social Science Research Journal*, 3(1), 321-340.
 34. Khan, Y., Rehman, A., Shah, T. U., & Khan, K. (2018). The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Firm's Productivity: A Comparative Study of Two Competing Firms having UN Global Compact Status. *The Discourse*, 4(2), 1-16.
 35. Khan, Y., Zafar, S., & Ayaz, M. B. (2022). The Effect of Firm Size, Investment Opportunity Set, and Capital Structure on Firm Value. *International Journal of Social Science & Entrepreneurship*, 2(2), 32-46.
 36. Ko, F.-s. (2022). Comparisons of a multi-regional trial for four or five regions by fixed effect model and random effect model about allocating sample size rationally into individual regions for a multi-regional trial. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, 1-21.
 37. Ma, C., Awan, R. U., Ren, D., Alharthi, M., Haider, J., & Kouser, R. (2022). The IFRS adoption, accounting quality, and banking performance: An evaluation of susceptibilities and financial stability in developing economies. *PLoS One*, 17(7), e0265688.
 38. Miah, M. S., Jiang, H., Rahman, A., & Stent, W. (2023). The impact of IFRS complexity on analyst forecast properties: The moderating role of high quality audit. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 28(1), 902-928.
 39. Morales-Díaz, J., & Zamora-Ramírez, C. (2018). The impact of IFRS 16 on key financial ratios: A new methodological approach. *Accounting in Europe*, 15(1), 105-133.
 40. Munteanu, A., Brad, L., Ciobanu, R., & Dobre, E. (2014). IFRS adoption in Romania: the effects upon financial information and its relevance. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 15, 288-293.
 41. Ndori Queku, Y., Adibura Seidu, B., Aneyire Kubaje, T., Boateng, K., Antwi-Agyei, E., Apeku, T., & Yamoah, K. (2023). IFRS adoption and tax revenue performance in Africa: does Africa need tax-targeted IFRS reforms? *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(2), 2212500.
 42. Nwaogwugwu, C. C. (2020). Effects of IFRS adoption on the financial performance and value of listed banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 8(4), 172-181.
 43. O Cualain, G., & Tawiah, V. (2023). Review of IFRS consequences in Europe: An enforcement perspective. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(1), 2148869.
 44. Pășcan, I.-D. (2015). Measuring the effects of IFRS adoption on accounting quality: A review. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 32, 580-587.
 45. Pfeffer, J., & Gerald, R. (1978). *Salancik. 1978. The external control of organizations: A resource dependence perspective*: New York: Harper & Row.
 46. Riaz, Z., Ray, P., & Ray, S. (2022). The impact of digitalisation on corporate governance in Australia. *Journal of Business Research*, 152, 410-424.
 47. Saeed, M. B. (2020). *Corporate Governance and Accounting Conservatism: Empirical Evidence from Emerging Markets of South Asia*. CAPITAL UNIVERSITY.
 48. Schmidhuber, L., Hilgers, D., & Hofmann, S. (2022). International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSASs): A systematic literature review and future research agenda. *Financial Accountability & Management*, 38(1), 119-142.
 49. Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1997). A survey of corporate governance. *The journal of finance*, 52(2), 737-783.
 50. Silva, R. L. M., & Nardi, P. C. C. (2020). Effects of mandatory adoption of IFRS on market liquidity in Brazil. *International Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Performance Evaluation*, 16(1), 1-24.
 51. Subramanian, S. (2018). Stewardship theory of corporate governance and value system: The case of a family-owned business group in India. *Indian Journal of Corporate*

-
- Governance, 11(1), 88-102.
52. Sukmawati, S., & Pujiningsih, S. (2022). IFRS Adoption Research in Indonesia: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Accounting and Investment*, 23(1), 95-113.
 53. Sun, Y., Guo, Y., & Wu, J. (2022). Comment on the selection of the fixed or random effect model in a study. *Translational Pediatrics*, 11(6), 1063.
 54. Watts, R. L., & Zimmerman, J. L. (1986). Positive accounting theory.
 55. Worku, S. E. (2022). The Impact of IFRS Adoption on Capital Structure:-Pre-Post Analysis of listed Banks in Ethiopia. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 8635-8655.
 56. Yousaf Khan, D., Ahmad, W., & Malik, F. (2021). Does Audit Quality Moderate the Nexus Between Corporate Governance and Accounting Earnings Quality in Emerging Economies? *Indian Journal of Economics and Business*, 20(4).
 57. Zaro, E., Flores, E., Fasan, M., Murcia, F. D.-R., & Zaro, C. S. (2022). Voluntary adoption of integrated reporting, effective legal system and the cost of equity. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 22(6), 1197-1221.